

A REVIEW ON MANNICH BASE- MOLECULAR SCAFFOLD

Tehseen Javed*, Santhanakrishnan K., Harish Kumar B., Sowmiya B., Dr. A. A. Kaaviya, Dr. Monish Raj R.

^{1,3}Assistant Professor, Dept. of Pharmacognosy, PERI College of Pharmacy.

²Assistant Professor, Dept. of Pharmaceutical Chemistry, PERI College of Pharmacy.

⁴Assistant Professor, Dept. of Pharmacology, PERI College of Pharmacy.

^{5,6}Assistant Professor, Dept. of Pharmacy practice, PERI College of Pharmacy.

Article Received on
09 August 2025,

Revised on 30 August 2025,
Accepted on 19 Sept. 2025,

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17214201>

*Corresponding Author

Tehseen Javed

Assistant Professor, Dept. of
Pharmacognosy, PERI
College of Pharmacy.

ABSTRACT

Mannich bases are the end products of Mannich reaction and are known as beta-amino ketone carrying compounds. Mannich reaction is a carbon-carbon bond forming nucleophilic addition reaction and is a key step in synthesis of a wide variety of natural products, pharmaceuticals, and so forth. Mannich reaction is important for the construction of nitrogen containing compounds. There is a number of aminoalkyl chain bearing Mannich bases like fluoxetine, atropine, ethacrynic acid, trihexyphenidyl, and so forth with high curative value. The literature studies enlighten the fact that Mannich bases are very reactive and recognized to possess potent diverse activities like anti-inflammatory, anticancer, antifilarial, antibacterial, antifungal, anticonvulsant, anthelmintic, antitubercular, analgesic, anti-HIV, antimalarial, antipsychotic, antiviral activities and so forth. The

biological activity of Mannich bases is mainly attributed to α, β -unsaturated ketone which can be generated by deamination of hydrogen atom of the amine group. However, a number of minor biological functions of Mannich bases have been reported, including their ability to control blood pressure or prevent platelet aggregation, their impact on parasites and ulcers, and their use as medications for mental health issues.

INTRODUCTION

The formation of C-C C bond formation in any organic synthesis is the Mannich reaction. Mannich base is formation of Aldehyde, ketones and a secondary amine make up the three-

component complex. antimicrobial, anti malarial, anti-HIV, anti-tubercular, anti-cancer, anti-inflammatory and anti-oxidant activities make them interesting pharmacologically. major impact on the individual optimization of time, temperature and percentage yield of synthesized compounds depends on The complexity of aldehydes, ketones and amines. Mannich bases and their derivatives are being developed with the aim of improving their physicochemical and drug like characteristics, which may have greater influence over pharmacological applications. Bioactivities, such as anti neoplastic, diuretic, antipsychotic, anticonvulsant, centrally acting muscle relaxant, antibacterial and antiviral ones, are present in the Mannich base of heterocyclic compounds. Carbazole mannich bases is identified as creation of prospective for anti-cancer drugs. Lewis's acids and bases, Bronsted acids, rare metal salts and organo catalysts can be used to catalyze the traditional Mannich reactions of aldehydes, ketones and amines. Because of the significant pharmacophores with promising activity, Mannich bases generated from acetophenone are particularly interesting and have shown significant potential in medicinal chemistry and drug development.

BIOLOGICAL ACTIVITIES

■ ANTIMICROBIAL ACTIVITY

A novel series of Mannich bases of 3-substituted-4-(5-nitro-2-furfurylidene)amino-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazoles 1(a-n) (Figure 1) was synthesized and screened for the antifungal activity against *C. albicans* by employing disc diffusion method using nitrofurazone and fluconazole as standard drugs for comparison. The results revealed that all the compounds were found to be least active as compared to nitrofurazone whereas compounds 1c, 1d, 1f, 1h, 1j, and 1n were found to have better antifungal activity as compared to fluconazole. Compound 1f substituted with methyl and chloro group has shown highest antifungal activity with 17 mm zone of inhibition which is higher than zone of inhibition of fluconazole, that is, 12 mm. These results enlighten the key role of chloro group towards antifungal activity.

FIGURE – 1.

Mannich bases of 2-(phenyl)-2-(morpholine-4-yl)-N-phenylacetamide 2(a-g) were synthesized (Figure 2) and screened for antimicrobial activity against various bacterial and fungal strains. Ciprofloxacin and clotrimazole were used as standard drugs for antibacterial and antifungal activities, respectively. From the synthesized compounds, 2c, 3-(4-chlorophenyl)-3-(morpholin-4-yl)-N-phenylpropanamide, has shown highest antibacterial activity against *S. epidermidis* with 20 mm of zone of inhibition as compared to ciprofloxacin with 15 mm. Compounds 2e, 3-(morpholin-4-yl)-3-(4-nitrophenyl)-N-phenylpropanamide, and 2f, 3-(4-methoxyphenyl)-3-(morpholin-4-yl)-N-phenylpropanamide, were found to have equipotent antibacterial activity as compared to ciprofloxacin against *K. pneumonia* and nonhemolytic *streptococcus*, respectively. The compounds 2d and 2e were found to have equipotent antifungal activity against *M. audouinii* and *C. albicans* as compared to clotrimazole. The compound 2c having 4-chlorophenyl has not contributed to antifungal activity.

FIGURE – 2.

■ ANTI-INFLAMMATORY ACTIVITY

Mannich bases of nicotinamide were synthesized with secondary amines like mefenamic acid, and diclofenac, in the presence of formaldehyde and hydrochloric acid. Anti-inflammatory activity was studied by hind paw oedema method using carrageenan as a phlogistic agent on Wistar rats. Nicotinamide, diclofenac, and mefenamic acid were used as standard drugs. Both the Mannich bases showed greater anti-inflammatory activity than the corresponding parent drugs.

FIGURE – 4 (Diclofenac).

Nicotinamide showed least anti-inflammatory activity. Mannich bases of diclofenac (MND) showed greater activity than Mannich bases of mefenamic acid (MNM). The order of anti-inflammatory activity was found as MND > MNM > diclofenac > mefenamic acid > nicotinamide. It appears that the synthesized Mannich bases showed synergistic anti-inflammatory activity.

Mannich bases of indole, derivatives were synthesized by reacting different derivatives of indole with various aromatic and heterocyclic amines in the presence of formaldehyde and dimethylformamide (FIGURE – 5). Anti-inflammatory activity was screened on albino rats of Wistar strains by carrageenan paw induced method. Diclofenac sodium was used as standard drug. Carrageenan suspension 0.9% in sodium chloride was injected in plantar region of hind paw and paw volume was measured with the aid of plethysmometer. It was observed that the newly synthesized Mannich bases possessing electron withdrawing groups (nitro and chloro) exhibited better anti-inflammatory activity.

FIGURE – 5.

▪ ANTHELMINTIC ACTIVITY

N-Mannich bases of benzimidazolyl substituted 1*H*-isoindole-1,3(2*H*)-dione 18(a–l) were synthesized (Figure 6). All the synthesized compounds were screened for anthelmintic activity by Watkins technique, against common Indian earthworm *P. posthuma*. Piperazine hydrochloride was used as standard drug. All the synthesized derivatives have shown significant anthelmintic activity whereas the derivatives substituted with different groups, that is, 18a (piperazino-), 18b (morpholino-), 18c (diphenylamino-), 18i (chloro), and 18j–l (nitro and dinitro) groups, showed better activity than other derivatives.

FIGURE – 6.

▪ ANTICANCER ACTIVITY

A series of novel Mannich bases of 2-propoxybenzylideneisonicotinohydrazide, were screened for the cytotoxicity studies against the A549 human lung adenocarcinoma. Dulbecco's modified eagle medium was used for the growth of cells and supplemented with glutamine, fetal bovine serum, penicillin, and streptomycin. Gemcitabine was used as standard drug. The viability of the cells was assessed by MTT assay. Cells were placed in 96-well plate and after 24 h they were treated with different test compounds. In each well MTT in phosphate buffer saline was added and incubated and then DMSO was added to each well and kept in incubator. From all the compounds synthesized, exhibited potential cytotoxic activity superior to that of the standard drug, gemcitabine.

FIGURE – 7.

Schiff-Mannich bases of fluoroquinolones, from antibacterial analogs were synthesized and screened for antitumor activity against L1210, CHO, and HL60 cell lines. The cell lines were maintained in RPMI 1640 medium supplemented with fetal bovine serum. The medium containing 5×10^3 cells was seeded into 96-well microplate and compounds to be tested were then added. Plates were incubated and MTT solution in PBS was added to each well. The plates were further incubated for 4 h and DMSO was added to the wells containing CHO cell lines. Dodecyl benzenesulfonate (10%) was added to cells containing L1210 and HL60. The optimal density of each well was measured at 570 nm. Among the synthesized compounds exhibited significant cytotoxic activity than the parent compound.

CONCLUSION

Mannich bases and their derivatives are found to have potent diverse activities. This review summarized various biological activities of Mannich base derivatives in present scenario. It can be concluded that Mannich bases have remarkable biological potential which is remaining unexplored. However this review would expectantly shed light on ways to raise the therapeutic worth and specificity of Mannich bases. This bioactive core has maintained the interest of researchers in gaining the most suggestive and conclusive access in the field of various Mannich bases of medicinal importance from last decades and also endorsed the researchers for design of novel heterocyclic/aryl derivatives for progress of new environment-friendly technology.

REFERENCES

1. *Advanced Organic Chemistry: Reactions, Mechanisms, and Structure*, John Wiley & Sons, New York, NY, USA, 3rd edition, 1985.
2. V. J. Belinelo, G. T. Reis, G. M. Stefani, D. L. Ferreira-Alves, and D. Piló-Veloso, "Synthesis of $6\alpha,7\beta$ -dihydroxyvouacapan-17 β -oic acid derivatives. Part IV: mannich base

- derivatives and its activities on the electrically stimulated guinea-pig ileum preparation,” *Journal of the Brazilian Chemical Society*, 2002; 13(6): 830–837.
3. S. Joshi, N. Khosla, and P. Tiwari, “In vitro study of some medicinally important Mannich bases derived from anti-tubercular agent,” *Bioorganic & Medicinal Chemistry*, 2004; 12(3): 571–576.
 4. L. Racane, V. T. Kulenovic, L. F. Jakic, D. W. Boykin, and G. K. Zamola, “Synthesis of bis -substituted amidino-benzothiazoles as potential anti-HIV agents,” *Heterocycles*, 2001; 55: 2085–2098.
 5. E. Kashiwama, I. Hutchinson, M.-S. Chua et al., “Antitumor benzothiazoles. 8.1 Synthesis, metabolic formation, and biological properties of the C- and N-oxidation products of antitumor 2-(4- aminophenyl)-benzothiazoles,” *Journal of Medicinal Chemistry*, 1999; 42(20): 4172–4184.
 6. S. R. Bhusare, R. P. Pawar, and Y. B. Vibhute, “Synthesis and antibacterial activity of some new 2-(substituted phenyl sulfonamido)-6-substituted benzothiazoles,” *Indian Journal of Heterocyclic Chemistry*, 2001; 11(1): 79–80.
 7. N. Raman, S. Esthar, and C. Thangaraja, “A new Mannich base and its transition metal (II) complexes—synthesis, structural characterization and electrochemical study,” *Journal of Chemical Sciences*, 2004; 116(4): 209–213.
 8. B. Kalluraya, R. M. Chimbalkar, and J. C. Hegde, “Anticonvulsant activity of nicotinyl\isonicotinyl substituted 1,2,4-triazol-5-thione Mannich bases,” *Indian Journal of Heterocyclic Chemistry*, 2005; 15(1): 15–18.
 9. M. Köksal, N. Gökhan, E. Küpeli, E. Yesilada, and H. Erdogan, “Analgesic and antiinflammatory activities of some new Mannich bases of 5-nitro-2-benzoxazolinones,” *Archives of Pharmacal Research*, 2007; 30(4): 419–424.
 10. Y. Ivanova, G. Momekov, O. Petrov, M. Karaivanova, and V. Kalcheva, “Cytotoxic Mannich bases of 6-(3-aryl-2-propenoyl)-2(3H)-benzoxazolones,” *European Journal of Medicinal Chemistry*, 2007; 42(11-12): 1382–1387.
 11. H. I. Gul, J. Vepsalainen, M. Gul, E. Erciyas, and O. Hanninen, “Cytotoxic activities of mono and bis Mannich bases derived from acetophenone against Renca and Jurkat cells,” *Pharmaceutica Acta Helvetiae*, 2000; 74(4): 393–398.
 12. M. Ashok, B. S. Holla, and B. Poojary, “Convenient one pot synthesis and antimicrobial evaluation of some new Mannich bases carrying 4-methylthiobenzyl moiety,” *European Journal of Medicinal Chemistry*, 2007; 42(8): 1095–1101.

13. S. N. Pandeya, D. Sriram, G. Nath, and E. De Clercq, "Synthesis, antibacterial, antifungal and anti-HIV activities of norfloxacin Mannich bases," *European Journal of Medicinal Chemistry*, 2000; 35(2): 249–255.
14. B. N. Singh, S. K. Shukla, and M. Singh, "Synthesis and biological activity of sulphadiazine Schiff's bases of isatin and their N-mannich bases," *Asian Journal of Chemistry*, 2007; 19(7): 5013–5018.
15. S. C. Vashishtha, G. A. Zello, K. H. Nienaber et al., "Cytotoxic and anticonvulsant aryloxyaryl Mannich bases and relate compounds," *European Journal of Medicinal Chemistry*, 2004; 39(1): 27–35.
16. E. Bennet-Jenkins and C. Bryant, "Novel sources of anthelmintics," *International Journal for Parasitology*, 1996; 26(8-9): 937–947.
17. D. Sriram, D. Banerjee, and P. Yogeewari, "Efavirenz Mannich bases: synthesis, anti-HIV and antitubercular activities," *Journal of Enzyme Inhibition and Medicinal Chemistry*, 2009; 24(1): 1–5.
18. J. S. Mulla, A. Y. Khan, S. I. Panchamukhi, M. A. Khazi, M. B. Kalashetti, and I. M. Khazi, "Synthesis and antitubercular activity of Mannich bases of imidazo [2,1-b] [1,3,4] thiadiazoles," *Indian Journal of Novel Drug Delivery*, 2011; 3(4): 289–295.
19. W. Malinka, P. Świątek, B. Filipek, J. Sapa, A. Jezierska, and A. Koll, "Synthesis, analgesic activity and computational study of new isothiazolopyridines of Mannich base type," *Farmaco*, 2005; 60(11-12): 961–968.
20. G. B. Barlin and C. Jiravinya, "Potential antimalarials. X. Di- Mannich Bases of 4-(7'-Trifluoromethyl-1',5'-naphthyridin-4'-ylamino)phenol and N-(4'-Diethylamino-1'-methylbutyl)-7-trifluoromethyl-1,5-naphthyridin-4-amine," *Australian Journal of Chemistry*, 1990; 43(7): 1175–1181.
21. M. K. Scott, G. E. Martin, D. L. DiStefano et al., "Pyrrole mannich bases as potential antipsychotic agents," *Journal of Medicinal Chemistry*, 1992; 35(3): 552–558.
22. M. L. Edwards, H. W. Ritter, D. M. Stemerick, and K. T. Stewart, "Mannich bases of 4-phenyl-3-buten-2-one: a new class of antiherpes agent," *Journal of Medicinal Chemistry*, 1983; 26(3): 431–436.
23. R. E. Karll and R. J. Lee, "Process and compositions," US Patent no., 1983; 4,384,138.
24. F. P. Otto, US Patent, US., 1972; 3: 649 229.
25. J. R. Dimmock and P. Kumar, "Anticancer and cytotoxic properties of Mannich bases," *Current Medicinal Chemistry*, 1997; 4(1): 1–22.

26. J.-X. Ji, L.-Q. Qiu, C. Wing Yip, and A. S. C. Chan, “A convenient, one-step synthesis of optically active tertiary aminonaphthol and its applications in the highly enantioselective alkenylations of aldehydes,” *The Journal of Organic Chemistry*, 2003; 68(4): 1589–1590.
27. P.-J. J. Huang, D. Youssef, T. S. Cameron, and A. Jha, “Microwave-assisted synthesis of novel 2-naphthol bis-Mannich Bases,” *Arkivoc*, 2008; 2008(16): 165–177.
28. M. Arend, B. Westermann, and N. Risch, “Modern variants of the Mannich reaction,” *Angewandte Chemie—International Edition*, 1998; 37(8): 1045–1070.
29. B. S. Holla, M. K. Shivananda, M. S. Shenoy, and G. Antony, “Studies on arylfuran derivatives. Part VII. Synthesis and characterization of some Mannich bases carrying halophenylfuryl moieties as promising antibacterial agents,” *Farmaco*, 1998; 53(8-9): 531–535.